

**Avisuality of Atomic Violence:
A Study of Keiji Nakazawa's
I Saw It (1972)**

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There were no bones left in my mother's ashes, as there normally are after a cremation. Radioactive cesium from the bomb had eaten away all her bones to the point that they disintegrated. The bomb had deprived me of my mother's bones.

—Keiji Nakazawa

The lack of detailed visual evidence of the bomb's effects reinforced this initial positive response. US occupation authorities censored reports from the city and suppressed the more horrifying films and photographs of corpses and maimed survivors. Americans initially saw only images of the awesome mushroom cloud.

—Paul Boyer

I'm going to show their faces to the bastards who started the war . . . and the bastards who dropped the bomb . . . I'm going to make this my final masterpiece! Dammit all! Dammit all!

—Keiji Nakazawa

What does it mean to be human?

The ghastly horrors of the nuclear blasts and their unacceptable effects on human beings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki question the human cost of atomic weapons. Unfortunately, the 1945 massacre of Japanese people remains one of the most brutal scars perpetually etched in human history. It was equally challenging to archive in any medium after most of the living witnesses disintegrated with the dropping of the a-bombs. Peace was restored at the cost of dismantled human bodies. Keiji's Nakazawa's firsthand witness, a 48-page graphic memoir *I Saw It* (1972), responds to the mechanical objectivity of photographs in the twenty-first century. It is also one of the first spectacles of a graphic reaction against the injustice faced by a Japanese artist-writer to speak about the unspeakable through his comic book. This paper intends to discuss the relevance of hand-drawn imprints to represent violence in an era of technologically advanced photographic accuracy. This paper aims to bring forth the politics of hibakusha, silencing the survivors from sharing their side of the story on the cataclysmic event of 1945. The research paper will also discuss the possibilities and scopes of the medium of comics as a counter-discourse resisting the invisible culture of hiding the truth of Japan beneath the infamous mushroom cloud. Finally, the paper also wishes to address the motif behind a defamiliarized representation of the banality

of violence through the beautifully colored panels of the text.

Violence Etched on the Human Body

The dropping of the atomic bomb on Hiroshima and Nagasaki was a sudden action taken by the US government. During the 1940s and 1950s, the culture of photography gradually formed toward becoming one of the most trustworthy mediums of delivering real news to the people against the backdrop of World War II. Without satellite facilities or advanced cameras, archiving the atomic blasts solely depended on first-hand experiences and witnesses. There was a famous photograph taken from above right after dropping the bomb. Still, there was no evidence of what happened beneath it as the atomic explosion destroyed everything.

Akira Mizuta Lippit, in her book *Atomic Light* (2005), talks about the need for a new mode of inscriptions to record the aftermath of the blasts in Japan. The blasts left their brutal mark by almost entirely destroying a nation. The graphic projection of such a horrific incident was carried by every living human being through various marks. The atomic bomb was printed on their body like a graphic design. Lippit writes, “Atomic irradiation can be seen as having created a type of violent photography directly onto the surfaces of the human body” (Lippit 2005, 92).

The atomic blasts took the lives of more than 250000 people (about half the population of Hiroshima and Nagasaki). In the following years, the impact of the radiation kept haunting the survivors with cancer, leukemia, and perpetual disability as its side effects. The International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons (ICAN), one of the leading non-governmental organizations in one of their archives, "Hiroshima and Nagasaki Bombings" describes, "The uranium bomb detonated over Hiroshima on 6 August 1945 had an explosive yield equal to 15,000 tonnes of TNT. It razed and burnt around 70 per cent of all buildings and caused an estimated 140,000 deaths by the end of 1945, along with increased rates of cancer and chronic disease among the survivors" (ICAN, web page). They also have given a detail how of a "slightly larger plutonium bomb exploded over Nagasaki three days later levelled 6.7 sq km. of the city and killed 74,000 people by the end of 1945. Ground temperatures reached 4,000°C and radioactive rain poured down" (ibid).

Within a few seconds, Hiroshima and Nagasaki faced the terror of being entirely wiped out from the world map as everything turned pitch black. The horror was unimaginable and unseen ever before. Lippit calls this "avisuality," "a visuality without images, an unimaginable visuality, and images without visuality" (Lippit 2005, 109). There cannot be any "authentic photography" of the atomic war because "the bombings themselves were

a form of total photography, testing the very visibility of the visual” (ibid). This avisuality, both as a concept and a construct, dragged on even after years of people returning to normalcy. The survivors still are living embodiments of the terrors forcibly imposed on them. Keiji Nakazawa’s nonfictional autobiography *I Saw It* acts as a “counterinscription” to give materiality to “avisuality” that Lippit discussed in her book. These books function as a resistance towards the avisuality caused by the atomic bomb.

Writer’s Responsibility

Yōtarō Konaka in her essay “Japanese Atomic-Bomb Literature” (1988) while discussing the emergence of atomic-bomb literature writes that the Holocaust was an infamous event where Jews were victimized. But in case of the dropping of the bombs, Japan was taught a lesson for starting the war. It was more of an attempt to end the war by punishing the Japanese people. The people of Japan were not victims, they were the ones initiating World War II. Therefore, it was the right decision to punish them for their deeds by experimenting the nuclear bombs on their people. Konaka pens down, “the two bombs that were dropped in August of 1945 not only ended the world war but also sounded a tragic alarm for mankind, ringing in the nuclear age” (Konaka 1988, 424). She also mentioned why it was so important to talk about the atomic blast to the world. While

reading Naruhiko Itō's first-hand witness in *Shikabane no machi/City of Corpses* (1948) where the author shares her experiences, the challenges she faced while writing the book. The book shares an interesting anecdote as Konaka also writes,

And corpses were lying all over, left and right, and in the middle of the road. Some were lying face upward and others face down, all of them had been headed toward the hospital. With their bulging eyes, swollen and battered lips, and bloated limbs, they were like hideous big rubber dolls. Weeping copiously, I recorded the image of those people on my heart. (ibid)

Itō records what she sees. It was a difficult task to write about people who have lost their forms but are somehow still alive like deadly huge plastic dolls. They were running towards the hospital without having any idea whether such a place existed anymore or not. This event was extremely difficult to write what Itō witnessed, the shedding of human flesh while they frantically marched towards getting medical attention. The question that naturally occurs to the mind of the reader is: How can someone write about such things? Why was it necessary to pass down such horror to the next generation? Itō answers **“Having seen these things, I must write about them at some time. It is a writer’s responsibility”** (ibid). The writer must have the responsibility of explaining what he/she has witnessed to pass it on to the future generation. More importantly, to remember how

the people of Nagasaki and Hiroshima were left to die.

Similar to Naruhiko Itō, Nakazawa Keiji, used the back of the then movie posters to draw cartoons. Amidst poverty, malnutrition, losing close ones, Keiji nourished his passion for drawing what he has seen as it is always the author's responsibility to write about the horror that people of Japan faced during the blasts. Keiji's descriptions of people after the blast are also like Itō. Also, there is one more writer, Masuji Ibuse whose novel *Koroi ame/ Black Rain* (1989) is in a way an inspiration for Nakazawa to continue his "Black" series consisting of: "The Black River Flows," "Beyond Black Silence," "A Flock of Black Pigeons," and "Black Flies." The "black" series presented presents the truth of the violent attacks in Japan.

Hibakusha, **Censorship and the Politics of Silencing**

In an interview, Asai Montofumi, the President of Hiroshima Peace Institute, asked Nakazawa about the discrimination he faced and how his experience when he was forced to live a painful life for eternity. In his book *Hiroshima: Autobiography of Barefoot Gen* (2010), Nakazawa responded that he had vehemently faced discrimination mainly because he was not allowed to discuss it. The atomic bomb survivors could not talk about their victimization openly. He also mentioned how people committed suicide while facing discrimination daily. Na-

kazawa also explained how people used to get agitated even if he was sad for other reasons and told him openly, “Don’t put on your bomb-victim face!” (Nakazawa, 2010, 275). Nakazawa feels that people looked down upon the victims of the atomic bomb in a threatening manner. People were not even ready to hear what the people of Japan had to say to them. Only after the World Convention to remove nuclear weapons in 1955 did the victims come out and start sharing their stories. However, Nakazawa still received questions like, “Did such things really happen?” (177). These remarks highlight people’s indifference toward knowing the truth of Japan.

ICAN, in one of their archives, titled, “The Hibakusha’s Decades Long Journey to Ban Nuclear Weapons,” painfully writes about Hiroshima that people are not ready to face, “Grotesquely wounded people, they were bleeding, burnt, blackened and swollen. Parts of their bodies were missing. Flesh and skin hung from their bones. Some with their eyeballs hanging in their hands. Some with their bellies burst open, their intestines hanging out. The foul stench of burnt human flesh filled the air” (ICAN, web page). This incident took place within 1.8 kilometers of the epicenter in Hiroshima.

This discrimination is known as *hibakusha* or the bomb affected people, or the survivors of the a-bomb in Japan. *Hibakusha* are the survivors who didn’t die instantaneously but carried forward the post-traumatic stress

disorder for years and eventually died of either cancer or leukemia. Elaine Natalie and Katie Yoon in their article, “Hibakusha: The Human Cost of Nuclear Weapons” (2021), discusses the negative sides of the coinage of the term. They write, “Fears of transmitting genetic illnesses further heightened the stigma associated with the hibakusha and their families, especially amid a leukemia wave during the aftermath of the bombings. Hibakusha were forcibly displaced and settled in “atomic slums” (genbaku suramu), experiencing years of deprivation and isolation” (Natalie and Yoon, 2021, web page). The last generation worked ceaselessly as advocates for the abolition of nuclear bomb and peace. Sadly, Japan did not sign the UN Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Events, which came into force on January 22, 2021.

In her book *Disaster Drawn: Visual Witness, Comics, and Documentary Form* (2016), Hillary Chute discusses that there was a censorship imposed in Japan by the U.S. government not to share the aftermath of the blasts. Christian Hong in her essay, “Flashforward Democracy: American Exceptionalism and the Atomic Bomb in *Barefoot Gen*” (2009) writes, “If not with unconcern then with a spirit of triumph, the US public, shielded in the early post-war years from graphic images of human ruin, hailed the atomic decimation of Japan” (Hong 2009, 126). The American response to the discrimination and the loss shows their apathy towards this small country whose life did matter less to their cause of posing as a

superior country in front of others. Quite surprisingly, it was put into effect by both the countries as the people of Japan too wanted to hide their tales of suffering as well as exposure to the atomic blasts. Therefore, the picture of the famous mushroom cloud after the blasts was symptomatic of the form of abstraction to promote the prowess of the United States government and their policies regarding the Cold War. Hong writes, how against “this image’s inadequacy as a representative the document, there have been countervailing attempts to privilege narration from a different deictic position, the “here” of the explosion versus the “there,” so as to present the neglected human dimension of the atomic bombings (ibid). Unlike Joe Sacco’s *Palestine* (1993) and Art Spiegelman’s *Maus*, Nakazawa’s story did not spread worldwide because the world policies and politics prevented the nation to raise its voice and point out their suffering to the world outside.

Perhaps for this reason as Chute discusses, there was a culture of silence being practiced by both the USA and Japan. Nakazawa had to go through a series of rejections before his graphic memoir got published in book form. He also had to publish them in erotic magazines to avoid censorship. His first graphic depiction of the atomic blast is “Pelted by Black Rain” (1988) which was published first in *Manga Punch*, a famous magazine for youngsters. This graphic account was a fictional one. Similar to the underground comix culture Nakazawa embraced the

subculture of manga in Japan to make his stories heard in front of the readers. Chute writes, “An angry, hard-boiled genre story about a young bomb victim, “Pelted by Black Rain” was completed in 1966 and rejected by major commercial publishers for years until *Manga Punch* took it on despite the editor’s expressed fears that both he and Nakazawa would be arrested by the CIA” (Chute 2016, 116). The book went through a series of rejections for its content. Being a victim of hibakusha for so long a desperate survivor such as Nakazawa went for the “third-rate,” the “lowbrow” magazines to express his views on the atomic bomb because **“even if it wasn’t one of the major magazines, wouldn’t it do if it just got read?”** (Chute 2016, 177; emphasis author’s). Finally, the publisher of the pornographic magazine *Manga Punch* took the risk and published his story.

Materializing Mother’s Bones: An Obituary

This book is not merely the artist’s responsibility for what he has seen but also an obituary where the artist wants to pay his mother’s debts. The book’s foundation lies in Nakazawa’s determination to recreate his mother’s bones that the bomb deprived him of. Chute discusses that Nakazawa needed to write this book as a tribute to his mother. Her decimation of bones was a turning point in the life of Nakazawa as he was not left with anything to hold on to. As a cartoonist, more importantly, an artist-writer, he wished to recreate his mother’s

bones that were deprived by the bomb. By drawing her on the page as Chute writes “creating work about witnessing the atomic bomb that preserves, archives, and makes material his experience in the face of the war that decimated the very materiality of his mother (Chute 2016, 125). Throughout the book, Nakazawa explains the importance of her mother in his life. He believes he would have been a criminal if his mom was not there as a support system that helped him pursue his study and love for cartoons. It was shocking when his mother died, and he came to Japan to collect her ashes. His life was finally taking a good turn when his mother died. Nakazawa remembers that he could not get anything back from his mother’s corpses at the crematorium. He has seen his father’s bones and his siblings’ skeletons, but his mother’s bones completely disintegrated. He writes, “I couldn’t find even her skull. Thinking this couldn’t be so, I rummaged for all I was worth. There were only occasional white fragments” (176). This incident played a crucial role in his life because he channeled his anger and frustration into writing a book about the atomic bomb. The deprivation of his mother’s bones propelled him to confront the nuclear bomb even more.

However, Chute asks an important question, “What does it mean to materialize history? What does it mean to mark out of a desire to render history concrete?” (Chute 2016, 26). There is an analysis that might be fitting to these questions, as sometimes drawing can be trans-

formed into something else, something bigger in the articulation of history. As William Kentridge writes in his essay “Double Lines,” “I have come to think of drawing as a form of projection. So it isn’t really a matter of making drawings of things in preparation for something else, but of *making drawing literally into other things*” (ibid). As Chute describes “Drawing is not just mimetic: it is its own artifact, substance, thing, phenomenology” (Chute 2016, 27). Drawing history from memories is an act of building something where you are not provided with any material to work on. Materializing “history through the work of marks on the page creates it as space and substance, gives it a corporeality, a physical shape—like a suit, perhaps, for an absent body, or to make evident the kind of space-time many bodies move in and move through; to make, in other words, the twisting lines of history legible through form” (ibid). In Nakazawa’s case, after his mother’s death, he decided finally to use manga as a weapon and a medium to relive his past and recreate them on the pages. However, like the Freudian concept of the fort-da game in Nakazawa’s narrative, there is a constant struggle between presence and absence in the process of re-creating because the blast not only left its impact on the places but also on people’s memories.

Enola Gay

Nakazawa’s, *I Saw It* visually depicts pika/flash when the child narrator first sighted the bomb, Enola Gay. The

sudden blow of the a-bomb causes spine-chilling darkness. As has been shown, the child narrator was shielded by the collision of a wall meant to kill him. While gradually regaining consciousness, the child narrator was overwhelmed by a pitch-dark silhouette painting the fate of the awe-stricken nation. The child, however, died of malnutrition and a radioactive environment around the nation. The blow of the a-bomb killed the woman the child narrator spoke to a few moments ago. Due to the high-pitched explosion, Nakazawa's mother gave birth to a daughter out of shock. Chute writes, "the panels of the bombing and its immediate aftermath unfold unhurriedly, cataloguing carefully, graphically, the effects of the bomb as the child observes them, each page a fresh encounter with bodies ruined in extraordinary ways" (Chute 2016, 124). The gross images and the brutality of the event with people's melted bodies are too difficult to watch. The grotesque images result from what Nakazawa has witnessed with his own eyes. The reality of such an event being expressed in a medium such as manga is challenging. Nakazawa also emphasizes the importance of form and farming in his narratives. As an artist-writer, he creates tension between the verbal and visual modalities. The readers are constantly agitated by the violence they expect to encounter in this book.

The Shadow of Photography

Paul Virilio in his book *War and Cinema: The Logistics of Perception* (1989) discusses that the nuclear bomb was a

light weapon that captured the face of trauma and left its print. Virilio writes, “If photography, according to its inventor Nicéphore Niépce, was simply a method of engraving with light” where “bodies inscribed their traces by virtue of their own luminosity, nuclear weapons inherited both the darkroom of Niépce and Daguerre and the military searchlight” (Virilio 1989, 8). There is a connection between nuclear warfare and photography. As mentioned earlier, Lippit in her book *Atomic Light* (2005) writes that there are many forms of documentaries on comics but only a few could “have pointed out that the bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki were *light-weapons* that prefigured the enhanced-radiation neutron bomb, the directed-beam laser weapons, and the charged-particle guns” (Lippit 2005, 92). Lippit writes, “a negative photography is possible in the atomic arena, a skiagraphy, a shadow photography. The shadow of photography” (Lippit 2005, 95). Hiroshima and Nagasaki both the places became shadows of photography.

Hillary Chute attaches her valuable comments that Nakazawa’s book was a counter-inscription to the camera culture of documenting. Chute writes, “its comics form signifies the bodily in the act of making marks against the techne of bodies marked and vaporized by the bomb’s light. To the removed, clinical, superlatively high-technology mode of inscription” (Chute 2016, 36). Chute has always been vocal about using comics as a counter-hegemony to the hegemonic world literature that denies comics its worth and treats comics as propa-

ganda. This shadow and light dichotomy forced Nakazawa to think of it as an option, an opportunity to witness and document. But Nakazawa relied on his memory and retraced everything, places, faces, or events. Materializing history from scraps thereby is a difficult job that Nakazawa did with passion because he had to make the trauma faced by his mother and the people of Japan visible to audiences worldwide. As Chute puts it Nakazawa's "desire is to make absent appear" (Chute 2016, 27). His comics and hand-drawn images are "counter burning," forcing his readers to engage, live and relive the realities of the blasts with him.

Thomas LaMarre in his essay, "Manga Bomb: Between the Lines of Barefoot Gen" (2010), writes about Nakazawa's unique style of writing this graphic narrative, as he writes, "its use of a conventional manga style to depict an event that is often deemed to be unrepresentable in its violence and trauma" (LaMarre 2010, 262). Nakazawa's fictional encounter of the a-bomb in Barefoot Gen "invites us to address not only the experience of survivors of Hiroshima but also to consider what manga expression brings to our understanding of the atomic bomb, war, and trauma" (ibid). The difference between *I Saw It* and *Gen* is everything is amplified in the latter and there is a sense of plasticity prevalent in *Gen*. LaMarre comments "Barefoot Gen works through the dynamics of the "plastic line", which contributes to its articulation of a politics in which vitality and resil-

ience do not appear to reside outside historical violence but seem to emerge with it” (ibid). To this Chute added, “The mark in Nakazawa’s work is both itself etched and longing to be etched, then—to burn inside a reader’s brain” (Chute 138).

Banality of Violence

It is almost next to impossible to talk about the survivors without mentioning the bomb. Lisa Yoneyama in her essay “On Testimonial Practices” (1999) writes, “identity of a hibakusha as a one-dimensional speaking subject was constituted by prioritizing the speaker’s ontological relationship to the bomb over his or her numerous other social relationships and positions” (Yoneyama 1999, 85). As if they lacked a life of their own. In *Hiroshima Traces*, Yoneyama further discusses, “One does not automatically become a witness (*shogensha*) or a storyteller (*kataribe*) simply by telling personal memories to public audiences. Such self-definition is accompanied by an attempt to critically intervene in given cultural and social contexts,” also, “the survivors assigned themselves the responsibility of conveying their personal memories of Hiroshima’s atomic obliteration to the general public, they did so out of a sense of urgency and with a great deal of self-awareness about the act of telling the past. In the process, many of these storytellers have come to question the given discursive arrangements that have structured first-person accounts of the atomic disaster”

(86). They reveal what they have faced out of self-awareness, a sense of duty to the nation and to become a part of the act of witnessing and, documenting their stories. Yoneyama writes, “the conventional narratives of Hiroshima and Nagasaki have often established the survivors as speaking subjects, while at the same time subjecting them to the regimes of truth production in national and legal-bureaucratic procedures, in medical and psychiatric investigations, and in the then-powerful oppositional discursive paradigm of the peace and antinuclear movement” (ibid). Yoneyama questions the politics of naming terms such as hibakusha, witness, story-teller, survivor and is trying to understand the contexts and purposes behind using them because “the awareness of becoming a witness/storyteller was necessarily linked to the decolonization of the language with which to speak of oneself” (ibid).

Yoneyama is sometimes scared that by making everything available to people, the actual pain somewhere becomes the prey of sensational news in today’s media. She discusses how the survivors were divided. Some related to the media exposure to share their stories with the rest of the world, while others shied away. She writes,

Yet some survivors have despised those who would thus expose their experiences, believing that the mass media’s sensationalized treatment of the survivors’ stories trivializes even the experience of nuclear dev-

astation by turning them into commodities. Such critics see publicly representing memories of the bomb as betraying the past moment of deaths and suffering that they alone have witnessed. (87-88)

Thereby, there is a reluctance to disclose what they have witnessed. The survivors' reluctance to speak is often regarded as authentication of the experience. Yoneyama mentions, "Children of survivors frequently claim that their parents completely suppressed stories of the bomb. A newspaper corporation worker, for instance, remembered that his father, whose entire family—including his first wife and all their children—was killed by the bomb, never uttered a word about the experience during his lifetime" (88). However, contrary to this reluctance and fear of being unable to express what he had seen, Nakazawa excels in documenting pain and trauma through this multimodal media. He was conscious of not making his work one-dimensional, as Yoneyama mentioned. That is why in the book, the sequence of atomic blasts appears only after page 249. The book presents trauma and suffering but is never dominated by the nuclear explosion alone. For example, as it has been already raised as an issue, *I Saw It* and *Gen* series have a tendency of assimilating violence with banality. As Hillary Chute simplifies it,

Their works are driven by such traumatic events, these events are not isolated; their works also bear witness through words and images to the everyday—

to the ordinary and to the scenes of enunciation that produce the acts of witness. These are works in which the objects of witness operate on scales both large and small. Motivated by crisis, they bear witness to lived experience that is often shaped by crisis but is not necessarily fully dictated by it. Nakazawa's work, for example, is highly attuned to the rhythms of daily family life both before and after the bomb. (Chute 2016, 29)

Thereby, these works function in many ways, the writer himself being a witness, as is Nakazawa, the writer penning down someone else's testimony, Spiegelman and Joe Sacco, and the writers participating in the act of witnessing, all of them did this.

Questioning the Medium and its Approaches

Interestingly, the characters are hauntingly pretty in a traumatic memoir such as Nakazawa's. Art Spiegelman, while discussing Nakazawa's oeuvre, wrote in the introductory section of the First Volume of *Barefoot Gen: A Cartoon Story of Hiroshima* (2004), "Gen haunts me. . . . Gen burned its way into my heated brain with all the intensity of a fever-dream" (Nakazawa 2004, 2). The event is gruesome but all the characters even after the blast appear beautiful with big eyes and pretty faces. The physiognomy of characters has been looked on with a negative angle by Spiegelman, as he writes, the characters often "leans to the cloyingly cute, with special

emphasis on Disney-like oversized Caucasian eyes and generally neotenic faces. Nakazawa is hardly the worst offender, though his cartoon style derives from that tradition. His craftsmanship is somewhat graceless, even homely, and without much nuance, but it gets the job done” (Nakazawa 2004, 2-3). Following the tradition of Robert Crumb’s tradition of telling the truth in a simpler style, Spiegelman concludes his introductory note by saying, “The drawing’s greatest virtue is straightforward, blunt sincerity. Its conviction and honesty allow you to believe in the unbelievable and impossible things that indeed happen in Hiroshima. It is the inexorable art of the witness” (3).

Marjane Satrapi’s memoir *Persepolis* (2004) represents a child’s perception of the 1979 Islamic Revolution in Iran through a minimalist approach. In *Comics Journal* Tim O’Neil criticized Marjane Satrapi’s approach in *Persepolis*. He argues, “Marjane Satrapi is not a very good cartoonist—I think I should say that up front so there’s no confusion on the matter” (O’Neil 2004, 37). In her book *Graphic Women: Life Narrative & Contemporary Comics* (2010), Hillary Chute defends Satrapi by saying, “Proficiency in realistic drawing is not necessarily the goal of any given narrative. Rather, graphic narrative is about the discursive presentation of time as space on the page” (Chute 2010, 146). Satrapi herself informs her interviewer David Hajdu, “Cartoonists shouldn’t have to be good. . . . The technical quality is not what matters”

(Hajdu 2004, 34-35). Therefore, the cartoons do not matter, but the audience must scrutinize and understand the story and narrative they bring along.

New Seeing: Defamiliarization

The question that needs to be raised is why and how comics offer a new way of seeing. How does comics present history in a defamiliarized way? How does the act of insisting on an event's authenticity and its defamiliarized representation go hand in hand? Julie Rivkin and Michael Ryan in their book *Literary theory: an anthology* (2004), writes,

literature would be considered not as a window on the world but as something with a palpability of its own which arrests the eye and merits study. The manipulation of representational devices may create a semblance of reality and allow one to have the impression of gazing through glass, but it is the devices alone that produce that impression, and they alone are what makes literature literary. (Rivkin and Ryan 2004, 3)

They both call this a new way of seeing that makes literature literary. Art Spiegelman in *Maus* provides a new way of seeing by applying the anthropomorphic approach. Joe Sacco captures the quotidian life of the middle east suffering and destruction with his unique ability to render past, present and various testimonies on the same

page same panel. It is a struggle to read Sacco's tags and understand his footnotes and humor simultaneously.

Interestingly, with Nakazawa, the approach is entirely different. His seeing brutality is gruesome when compared with others. He has witnessed people's peeled skins, pus, wounds, and corpses like never before. He presents a new way of seeing injuries that would force the reader to be hooked on the pages and not shy away from or ignore such violence. Hillary Chute's explanatory commentary would be highly essential as she writes,

The first has to do with visual witnessing, the way that comics can offer an absorptive intimacy with their narratives while defamiliarizing received images of history. *I Saw It* and "Maus" are both narratives of terror that devolve on images of terror: the zombie-like, decomposing citizens of Hiroshima that Nakazawa witnessed firsthand; and the corpses, both pictured and implied, that people the Spiegelman son's visual reconstruction of his father's death-camp testimony. We might think of approaching World War II, after the broad silence that surrounded the war in America and in Japan, as mandating afresh Shklovsky's "new seeing" of reality. Comics picks up steam in the early 1970s as this new seeing. (Chute 2016, 142)

She also writes, "Motivated by the urgencies of re-seeing or re-visioning the war, comics sought to defamiliarize

received images of history, and also to communicate, to circulate in realms of the popular” (ibid). WWII came up with violence in abundance, and people witnessed trauma like never before. Such trauma is so extreme that people are numbed by it. Expressing them in words or drawing photos reminded them of the trauma they wanted to forget and get on with what they had. However, victims and survivors like Nakazawa felt the urge to make the world accustomed to the culture of expressing what they had seen and faced. Nakazawa, like his contemporaries, made violence banal, a perpetually lived reality for the rest of his life, and a new way of seeing and reliving those memories by making the invisible visible to the eyes of the people, by making his mother’s bones recreated on the pages.

Using this medium, an artist-writer can recreate lost bodies inside the drawn lines of comics. The characters are resurrected on the page through various marks. Chute writes, “The corporeality of the work comes to stand in for the missing corporeality of the dead parent, eviscerated by war” (142). Both Anja Spiegelman and Kimie Nakazawa survived the war. However, it eventually killed them. Spiegelman’s mother committed suicide in 1968, while Nakazawa’s mother died of leukemia in 1966. Therefore, “the Holocaust is motivation for Spiegelman to reconstruct Holocaust testimony” and for Nakazawa, “the decimation of his mother’s body from atomic radiation—its complete deconstitution—is also the reason

he decides to embark on a career of testimonial visibility” (142-3).

To conclude, the research paper aims to highlight the role of comics and the discursive potential of choosing a memoir as its subject. Chute’s commentary is concurrent with the theme as she writes, “The spatial features of comics, such as its activation of the space between word and image and its erection of literal drawn frames alongside its breaking and violation of them, presents a grammar that can inscribe trauma not just thematically” but also visibly through words and images (Chute 2016, 34-35). Thereby, the spatial features of comics helps the artist-writer build his narrative and materialize his memory. Interestingly, every aspect associated with comics helps the writer and reader understand different approaches and decode hidden meanings from the format. Nakazawa’s use of strokes, colors, pages, even smudgy page numbering, framing, dismembered panels, mushroom thought balloons, and this entire grammar structure of comics help the artist-writer build a narrative opportunity for the readers to understand the representation of violence throughout the text.

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